

time 20–30 minutes). The negative error exceeds to -0.38% when the duration of digestion is an hour at 80°.

The positive error for indium was observed in binary mixture of Hg(II) and In(III) only. Mercury(II) was estimated by masking In(III) with ammoniacal EDTA. The positive error might be due to slight solubility of Hg(II) dithiocarbamate in ammoniacal EDTA which is coprecipitated later on. The results of Hg(II) are better than -0.5%. The error of indium(III) dithiocarbamate varies in between +0.18 to +0.24%. The determination of indium in binary mixture (Ag, Hg, Pb, Cu and Bi) required acid treatment which makes the estimation slightly lengthier, inspite of this, the determination of indium is fast and accurate.

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Solvent Extraction Studies of Vanadium(V) in presence of N-p-methoxybenzoyl-N-p-methyl-phenylhydroxylamine and Thiocyanate

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THE recent interest in mixed-ligand complexes has stimulated the development of new methods of separation and analysis of metals¹⁻⁴.

Binary complexes of vanadium(V)-arylhydroxylamine systems^{5,6} produce blue/reddish-violet 1:2 complexes having the absorption maxima between 510-550 nm. A few mixed-ligand vanadium(V)-oxinate complexes^{7,8} have also been reported.

An account of the spectrophotometric studies on the formation of a ternary complex of vanadium(V) with N-p-methoxybenzoyl-N-p-methyl-phenylhydroxylamine (I)⁹ and thiocyanate is presented in this paper. The reagent (I) is found to form extractable blue-violet binary complex (λ_{max} at 540 nm at high acidity) with the metal. The extraction of the dark blue-violet vanadium(V) mixed-ligand complex in presence of thiocyanate takes place in the pH range (0.8-2.2) as well as in the acid range of 2-4N HCl and is stable over 4 hours at room temperature. The complex absorbs maximum at 570 nm. A hyperchromic effect followed by bathochromic shift in the absorption maxima occurred for the formation of mixed-ligand complex. Different extraction constants ($\log K_{ex}$, $\log K_d$ and $\log K_{mix}$) have been evaluated.

Experimental

Reagents, Solutions and Apparatus :

The reagent (I) (m.p. 128-30°) was prepared following the method described in monograph⁹. Solutions of the reagent(I) was prepared in A.R. chloroform.

An aqueous solution of vanadium(V) was prepared from A.R. ammonium meta-vanadate and the solution was standardised volumetrically¹⁰.

All the reagents, chemicals, solvents etc. used in the spectrophotometric measurements were of A.R. grade or spectro-grade quality.

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm glass cells was used for the absorbance measurements. All pH-measurements were made with Elico (model LI-10) pH meter.

Extraction Procedure of Vanadium(V) :

An aliquot of the metal solution (1 ml of 0.1 mg/ml solution) was transferred into 100 ml of separatory funnel, followed by dilute acid (6N HCl) and water to achieve pH 1.8 and the aqueous phase of 15 ml. 5 ml of 0.5% (w/v) reagent(I) solution and 10 ml chloroform were added and shaken for 10 minutes. To this solution, 5 ml of 2% standard ammonium thiocyanate solution was added and the mixture was thoroughly shaken for another 5 minutes. The resultant dark blue-violet complex in the chloroform layer was drained out and the aqueous layer was washed twice with 5 ml portion of the solvent, the extracts, combined dried and transferred to a 25 ml standard flask. The volume was made up with the solvent and the absorbance was measured at 570 nm against chloroform as blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance Spectra : The absorbance spectra of the mixed complex [V(V)–I–SCN] [V(V)= $7.86 \times 10^{-5} M$] extracted in chloroform at pH 1.8 shows maximum absorption at 430 nm and 570 nm. Subsequent measurements were made at 570 nm against solvent as blank where the reagent had no absorption.

Effect of Acid Concentration : The stable mixed-ligand complex is formed at both pH (0.8-2.2) and high acidity (2-4N HCl) ranges, having same absorption maxima, molar absorptivity ($\epsilon=7260 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 570nm) and the Sandell's¹¹ sensitivity ($0.007 \mu\text{gV/cm}^2$).

Effect of Reagent (thiocyanate) : For the formation of mixed complex of V(V), 5 ml of 1% ammonium thiocyanate solution was found sufficient for full development of color for 4 ppm of the metal. Very large excess of thiocyanate concentration or simultaneous addition with ligand decreases the color intensity.

Calibration curve, Optimum range and Photometric error :

It is found that the system obeys Beer's law over the concentration range of 0.5-12 ppm and the optimum concentration range as obtained from the Ringbom's¹² plot is from 1-10 ppm. The relative analysis error per 1% absolute photometric error according to Ayres¹³ equation is found to be 2.70 in all the cases.

Effect of diverse ions : Interferences due to different ions were less at high acidity in comparison to that at low pH range. So during analysis, the interferences were minimised by adjusting the acidity. Ti(IV), Fe(III), Cu(II), W(VI), Mo(VI), Nb(V), Zr(IV) interfere with different tolerance limits. Heavier transition metals like Os(VIII), Re(VII), Pd(II) and Pt(IV) were found to interfere. Tolerance limit of Ti(IV) could be increased by using NaF and the interference due to Fe(III) might be avoided either by increasing acid concentration of the solution or by extracting it in solvent ether at 6-8N HCl. Mo(VI) was removed by ethyl-xanthate extraction¹⁴. Tolerance limit of W(VI) and Zr(IV) was increased by the addition of phosphate and that of Cu(II) and Cr(III) was increased by the addition of EDTA at low acidity.

Procedure for High Speed Steel Analysis :

(BAS, 64b) - contains 1.99% of V.

0.6g of the sample was dissolved in dilute H_2SO_4 (1:4) and evaporated to a syrupy mass, repeating the process twice with 5 ml portion of concentrated H_2SO_4 and once with 5 ml concentrated HNO_3 . The solution was heated to dense white fumes, cooled, diluted to 50 ml and then boiled to dissolve any solid matter. It was filtered and the residue washed several times with hot water. The solution was made upto 250 ml volume in a standard flask.

Transfer an aliquot of the solution and oxidise with 0.1% KMnO_4 solution. The general procedure was followed for extraction and the extract was washed with 2N HCl to back extract Fe(III) into the aqueous phase. The absorbance of the extract thus obtained was measured at 570 nm and the percentage of vanadium in the sample was found to be 1.950%.

Composition and Extraction Constants of the Mixed-Ligand Complex System :

In view of finding the ratio of metal to reagent (I) in presence of a constant excess of thiocyanate solution both Job's¹⁵ and molar ratio¹⁶ method as well as absorptiometric method^{7,8,17,18} are applicable.

For Job's and molar ratio methods, equimolar solutions ($9.825 \times 10^{-4} M$) of vanadium(V) and reagent (I) in chloroform were used and a fixed concentration of thiocyanate (5 ml of 2% solution for each extraction) was maintained. The experimental plot indicates the metal to ligand ratio as 1:2. The result is verified

absorptiometrically i.e., from the plot of $\log \frac{E}{E_{max} - E} - pH$

vs $\log [\text{HR}]_{org}$ and the $\log K_{ex}$ is thus obtained from the intercept on the ordinate and the value is 6.20, using the equation :

$$K_{ex} = \frac{[\text{VO}(\text{R})_2\text{OH}]_{org} [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{VO}_2^+]_{aq} [\text{HR}]_{org}^2} = \frac{D_0 [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{HR}]_{org}^2} \text{ where } D_0 \\ = \frac{[\text{VO}(\text{R})_2\text{OH}]_{org}}{[\text{VO}_2^+]_{aq}} = \frac{E}{E_{max} - E}$$

and E_{max} = maximum absorption

E = absorption for the amount of HR at the point in question.

The above relation can be represented as,

$$\log \frac{E}{E_{max} - E} - pH = \log K_{ex} + 2 \log [\text{HR}]_{org}$$

The ratio of vanadium(V) to thiocyanate could not be determined by applying Job's and molar ratio methods but was determined absorptiometrically. The measurement of absorbance of the extracts obtained by varying the concentration of thiocyanate (under respective λ_{max} and pH) at a constant excess of I (5 ml of 0.5% solution in chloroform for each extraction) and

V(V) of $7.86 \times 10^{-5} M$, the plot of $\log \frac{E_A - E_{min}}{E_{max} - E_A}$ vs \log

$[\text{SCN}^-] - pH$ gave a st. line with a slope of unity which indicates the metal : thiocyanate ratio as 1:1 and the $\log K_A$ is obtained from the intercept by extrapolation and the value is 4.88.

Hence the equilibrium extraction constant of the mixed-ligand system, $\log K_{m:ex:ed}$ at room temperature is obtained from $\log (K_{ex} K_A)$ and the value is 11.08. The $\log K_{m:ex:ed}$ was also determined directly from the

absorptiometric plot of $\log \frac{E}{E_{max} - E}$ vs $2 \log [\text{HR}]_{org}$

+ $\log [\text{SCN}^-] - pH$, gave a st. line and the value is obtained from the intercept by extrapolation and is found to be 11.0.

K_A and $K_{m i x e d}$ are determined using the equations:

$$K_A = \frac{[\text{VO}(\text{R})_2 \text{SCN}]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{VO}(\text{R})_2 \text{OH}]_{\text{org}} [\text{SCN}^-] [\text{H}^+]},$$

(which is equivalent to)

$$\log \frac{E_A - E_{m i x}}{E_{m a x} - E_A} = \log K_A + \log [\text{SCN}^-] - \text{pH}$$

and

$$\log D_{m i x e d} = \log \frac{E}{E_{m a x} - E} = \log K_{m i x e d}$$

$$+ 2 \log [\text{HR}]_{\text{org}} + \log [\text{SCN}^-] - \text{pH}.$$

The value of $\log K_{m i x e d}$ is quite in agreement with the previous result.

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Leucoanthocyanins from *Cassia javanica* Root Bark

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FROM the ethanolic extract of the root bark of *Cassia javanica* two anthraquinones and their glycosides had been isolated and the chemistry of these compounds reported earlier¹.

In the present communication isolation and structural studies of two new leucoanthocyanins (I) and (II) are being reported.

Plant of the genus *Cassia* are well known for their medicinal value² and are also rich sources of flavonoids and anthraquinones^{3,4,5}.

The root bark of *Cassia javanica* was collected from a matured tree in the University campus. The dried powdered root bark was extracted with acetone, the extract concentrated under reduced pressure and poured into excess of cold water when a brown mass deposited which was filtered. The precipitate and filtrate were worked up separately.

The water insoluble portion was extracted with ether and ethyl acetate respectively. Ether fraction contained a flavonol, quercetin, which was confirmed by mp, mmp, derivatization and spectral studies⁶. Ethyl acetate fraction was concentrated and light petrol (40-60) was gradually added and the coloured sticky solid first separating was discarded. Further addition of petrol yielded the leucoanthocyanin(I). The process was repeated several times in order to obtain an almost colourless sample, m. p. 290°(d.).

The water soluble portion was concentrated under reduced pressure and extracted with ethyl acetate in a continuous liquid-liquid extractor. Ethyl acetate extract was concentrated and petrol was gradually added and the coloured sticky solid first separated was discarded. Further addition of petrol yielded leucoanthocyanin(II). The process was repeated several times till pure leucoanthocyanin was obtained, melting at 200°(d.).

Leucoanthocyanin (Compound I) :

Compound (I) $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{11}$ has $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 120$ (ethanol); R_f 0.46 (PC, BuOH : AcOH : H_2O :: 4:1:5) and 0.38 (TLC, Benzene : EtOAc :: 1:1) spray vanillin in HCl [6]. λ_{max}^{EtOH} 278 nm. $\text{IR}_{\nu_{max}}^{KB}$ 3450, 2900, 1650, 1540, 1130-1050, 850 and 820 cm^{-1} . Formed acetate with Ac_2O /pyridine m.p. 205° and methyl ether ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$) m.p. 180°.